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The ATV – UTV Stress and Strain Survey: A Pilot Study

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ABSTRACT

All-terrain vehicles (ATVs) and utility terrain vehicles (UTV or side-by-sides) are used in many industries for their versatility. The agriculture sector is a frequent user, giving operators the ability to access lands that would otherwise be inaccessible other than by foot or horseback. Operating ATVs and UTVs have been associated with injuries and fatalities due to rollovers, collisions, and loss of control (LOC) events. Experts have reported that ATV hazards are due to vehicle design, reduced safety features, high center of gravity, and a short wheelbase that compromise overall vehicle stability. The Montana Weed Control Association (MWCA) is a statewide organization where members frequently use both vehicles on the job. Investigators developed a pilot study to identify stress and strains that may influence a riders' ability to control and safely operate their ATV or UTV. A 20-question online survey was completed by 54 MWCA members for a 30% response rate. Researchers found that upper extremities and the back were common areas of fatigue. ATV riders reported more fatigue in the legs compared to UTV drivers. The legs were another common site for pain, followed by the buttock and thighs. One-half of UTV drivers reported no pain. Of those subjects reporting vehicle related pain, 35% reported the head and neck were the most common areas. This pilot study provides essential subjective reporting of stress and strain that can be followed up with future research to measure and evaluate stress and strain associated with ATV and UTV use.

1. INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

The ATV Safety Institute (ASI) estimated that more than 11 million Off-Highway Vehicles (OHVs) were used by 35 million Americans for both recreation (78%) and work (22%) (ASI, 2018). The most popular OHVs are ATVs and UTVs. While these vehicles are used by many people and fulfill multiple purposes, they are not without risk (Neves et al., 2018). The Consumer Product Safety Commission (CPSC) reported that there were 2,258 total deaths involving OHVs between the years 2015-2017 and more than 15,000 deaths since 1982 (2020). In addition to the loss of life, there are an estimated 400,000 injuries per year with approximately 100,000 who seek medical care at emergency room departments in hospitals across the United States (US) (CPSC, 2020). The

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accidents and deaths of agricultural ATV-related accidents have been fairly well studied (Fawcett et al., 2016; Gilkey, 2019; Neves et al., 2018).

In the US, ATV related fatalities make up less than one-percent of all occupational fatalities (Helmkamp, Marsh and Aiken, 2011). However, the expanding use and popularity of ATVs in agriculture and other industries have led to a 300% increase in occupational related fatalities between 1992 and 2007 (Helmkamp, Marsh and Aiken, 2011). It was estimated that 65% of all ATV worker-related fatalities occurred in the agricultural sector (Helmkamp et al., 2012). In a review of workers' compensation claims in Montana from 2007 through 2012, it was found that the agricultural sector comprised of 59% of all claims with another business 15 sectors reporting claims as well (Lagerstrom et al., 2015). The accidents and injuries related to OHVs are not limited to the US. For example, in New Zealand, Quadbike (ATV)-related fatalities accounted for between 8% to 19% of all work-related fatalities (Shulruf & Balemi, 2010). Liddle et al. (2020) reported that approximately 1,500 Australian ATV users visit emergency rooms each year due to accidents and resulting injuries with approximately 10 – 15 deaths. In Sweden, investigators reported a threefold increase in the number of fatalities when comparing time intervals from 2003-2007 to 2013-2017 (Edlund et al., 2020).

Known risk factors for LOC events and/or accidents included going too fast, terrain slope (going up, down, or across hills), turning too sharp, carrying a passenger, and riding or driving on paved roads (Gilkey, 2019; Gilkey and Brazile, 2021). Despite these known risk factors, there has been little research carried out to identify and/or measure physical and/or mental stresses associated with operating ATVs and UTVs that could play a role in LOC events. Investigators have looked at ATV related whole-body vibration (WBV) and mechanical shock associated with back pain (Essien et al., 2016). Another study investigated body pain associated with ATV use by looking at New Zealand farmers (Milosavljevic et al., 2010). Researchers found lower back pain was the most common complaint being reported by 67% of the farm ATV riders. Neck pain was the second most common pain affecting 42% of users followed by upper back pain afflicting 25%. Study subjects reported persistent pain up to 12 months after the farmers' lambing season (Milosavljevic et al., 2010). It should be noted, 95% of the ATV and UTV accidents in Australia and New Zealand involved older working populations, whereas in the US, the majority of accidents occur among younger populations (Carman et al. 2010; Goldcamp et al., 2006; Moroney et al., 2003). We believe that further investigation is needed to evaluate stresses and strains among user populations with varied capabilities that may play a role in LOCs and accidents.

A literature review looking at ATV use in agriculture concluded that minimal research has been done to explore riders' interactive risk associated with ATVs and LOC events (Neves et al., 2018). Previous research focused on evaluating risk factors of LOC events, accidents, injuries, and fatalities. The leading cause of fatality during a LOC event has been not wearing a helmet (Lagerstrom et al., 2016). This pilot study was developed to identify rider perceived stress and strain associated with ATV and/or UTV use among a group of frequent OHV users in Montana.

The pilot study aims were to 1) identify and characterize ATV and UTV users within MWCA, 2) identify and distinguish basic patterns among this group of agricultural workers, and 3) identify and describe physical and/or mental stresses and strains associated with vehicle use. The primary study hypothesis was that parameters of stress and strain would not vary by gender, age, or vehicle type. To accomplish this, the investigators partnered with MWCA. The MWCA is an organization that serves all 56 count of the state and primarily uses ATVs and UTVs for herbicide application. The MWCA consists of more than 700 members distributed across seven regions of Montana serving all 56 counties.

2. METHODS

A 20-question anonymous survey was developed to investigate perceptions of stress and strain among MWCA ATV and UTV users. The survey was approved by the Institutional Review Board (IRB) at the university. Nine of the questions were structured as statements with respondents reporting their perceived levels of agreement using a Likert scale; 1 = highly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = neither agree nor disagree, 4 = agree, and 5 = highly agree (Likert, 1932). Descriptive questions comprised of seven items looking at gender, age, vehicle type, average hours operated in a week, vehicle modifications, seasons, and terrain type. Health and mental stresses were investigated using four questions in the form of statements, how they would rate their general health, ability to easily evaluate the landscape, reaction time, and balance control. Stress and strain responses were investigated using questions about fatigue and pain associated with specific body parts and/or activities. Researchers entered the survey in to the online data collection tool Qualtrics. The MWCA distributed the survey link through email and by phone to primary supervisors throughout the state. Raw data were downloaded in Microsoft Excel, aggregated, and moved to Minitab Statistical Package 20.4 for analysis. Descriptive statistics and frequencies were generated using Minitab. Associations between variables were investigated using non-parametric Chi-square statistical test and general linear model (GLM).

3. RESULTS

The pilot study survey resulted in 54 responses over a one-month period. While there were 54 responses not every respondent answered every question. The link connected respondents to the Qualtrics site for survey completion. The survey did not reach the 700+ members of MWCA and only went to 181 members for a 30% response rate. Spraying weeds accounted for 85% of tasks in which respondents participated using the ATV and/or UTV (Table 1). Ninety-four percent of the participants were classified into the 46 to 65-year age group. Males comprised 65% of respondents and most users operated both types of vehicles (Table 1). ATV and UTV users reported that the majority of their vehicle operations required that they ride or drive on off-road brush or dirt and gravel surfaces 78% and 80% respectively (Table 1).

There was a considerable agreement with most questions asked with an overall mean score of 3.9 (Table 2). Only one question had a low mean score of 2.0 pertaining to wearing a helmet (Table 2). The survey participants agreed or highly agreed that they could survey the landscape while traveling (mean score 4.4), maintained their balance (mean score 4.4), had enough strength to maintain control of their vehicle (mean score 4.5), and were able to shift their weight when making turns (mean score 4.5) (Table 2).

The overall mean scores for pain and fatigue associated with both ATV and UTV were 3.3 and 3.5 respectively (Table 3). Fatigue wasn't felt on an average day by 65% riders whereas, approximately 30% reported experiencing some fatigue and 35.3% reported pain (Table 3).

Table 1 – ATV and UTV Rider Characteristics and Use Patterns

Variable	Characteristics	Frequency (n)	Percent
Gender	Male	34	65%
	Female	18	35%
Age (yrs)	18 - 24	2	4%
	25 - 35	7	13%
	36 - 45	9	17%
	46 - 55	13	24%
	56 - 65	20	37%
	More than 65	3	6%
What do you normally ride ATV or UTV (side-by-side or ROV) or Both?	ATV	13	25%
	UTV (side-by-side or ROV)	15	29%
	Both	24	46%
On average, how many hours do you ride in a week?	<=10	30	59%
	11 to 20	6	12%
	21 to 30	8	16%
	31+	7	14%
Has your vehicle been modified for any of these tasks?	Spraying weeds	46	85%
	Building/maintaining fence	9	17%
	Plow/blade snow	10	19%
	Irrigation work	8	15%
	Moving animals	5	9%
Surfaces the you normally travel	Paved road	19	35%
	Dirt/gravel road	43	80%
	Brush off-road	42	78%
	Hill 30-45 % Grade	30	56%
What seasons do you use your ATV/UTV? select all that apply	Spring	50	93%
	Summer	51	94%
	Fall	45	83%
	Winter	23	43%

Table 2 – Mean Scores for Select Questions

Statements	N	Mean Score	95% CI
I always wear a helmet when riding?	53	2.0	1.62 - 2.42
How would you rate your general health?	54	4.3	4.09 - 4.43
How would you rate your reaction time?	53	4.1	3.94 - 4.32
I easily evaluate the landscape on which I am traveling across?	51	4.4	4.12 - 4.66
I easily maintain my balance?	53	4.4	4.11 - 4.61
When mounting or dismounting my UTV/ATV, I rarely find it fatiguing?	52	3.8	3.42 - 4.23
I always have enough strength to maintain control of my vehicle?	52	4.5	4.23 - 4.74
I never have numbness/tingling in my hands or fingers after riding?	51	3.5	3.12 - 3.98
When making turns, I find it easy to shift my weight?	53	4.5	4.32 - 4.73

Table 3 –Fatigue and Pain on Average Day

Strongly Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither agree nor Disagree	Somewhat Agree	Strongly Agree
When riding on an average day I feel NO fatigue?				
5	10	3	24	10
9.6%	19.2%	5.8%	46.2%	19.2%
Mean: 3.5			95% CI 2.19 - 4.74	
When riding on an average day I feel NO pain?				
5	13	5	16	12
9.8%	25.5%	9.8%	31.4%	23.5%
Mean: 3.3			95% CI 1.98 - 4.70	

Pain and fatigue were similar for shoulder and lower back, 43% and 47% respectively, and they were the most reported specific body areas were affected (Figure 1). The differences reported between operators' pain and fatigue were seen in legs, feet, arms, lower back, and shoulders at 5.5%, 5.6%, 5.5%, and 7.4% respectively (Figure 1).

Figure 1 – Pain and Fatigue Location

The mean hours of vehicle operation for females were 21.0 hours whereas males were 12.7 hours (Figure 2) however, 59% reported less than 10 hours per week vehicle use (Table 1). As the participants increased in age, their hours of vehicle use also increased to a maximum of 20.5 hours (Figure 2).

Figure 2 – Hours of Operation by Vehical Type, Gender, and Age

The areas of the body most frequently reported to experience fatigue were in the shoulder and lower back for both vehicles (Figure 3). Fatigue patterns overall seem to be similar for both ATVs and UTVs. Use of the ATVs had the highest upper extremity fatigues in the shoulder and arm 62% and 46% respectively compared to UTVs (Figure 3). UTV drivers reported no knee fatigue yet nearly a quarter of ATV riders did report fatigue in the knees.

Figure 3 – Fatigue by Specific Body Location and Vehicle Type

The pain by location was quite different compared to the fatigue (Figure 3 vs Figure 4). ATV riders reported the most frequent pain in the legs, feet, and buttocks (Figure 4). UTV riders appear to experience less pain overall with none reported in knees and thighs (figure 4). UTV drivers reported a slightly higher frequency of neck pain than ATV riders 38% and 33% respectively (Figure 4). Half of the UTV users reported no pain in contrast to 87% of ATV users reporting wide distribution of pain (figure 4).

Figure 4 - Pain by Specific Body Location and Vehicle Type

4. DISCUSSION

This pilot study yielded insight into perceived stresses and strains associated with operating both ATVs and UTVs. The primary study hypothesis was that parameters of stress and strain would not vary by gender, age, or vehicle type. We reject that hypothesis because there was variability in reported fatigue and pain patterns. Associations of genders, age and vehicle type were to pain and fatigue were not statistically significant ($p\text{-value} > 0.05$) however, descriptive analysis clearly showed a higher frequency of pain among ATV users in comparison to UTV users (Figure 4). ATV operation appears to have greater stress and strain associated with use. ATV operators reported a similar pattern of fatigue but more pain. The ATV riders reported pain affecting all areas identified (Figure 4). A proposed explainer theory suggests ATVs are more physically demanding to operate compared to UTVs. ATVs are uniquely designed with a straddle seat, motorcycle-like handlebars, hand controls, and low inflation tires whereas, UTVs are designed more like the automobile with a bucket seat, steering wheel, foot controls, and roll-cage for added safety (Gilkey, 2019). The UTV is generally heavier, wider, and lower to the ground resulting in a lower center of gravity, increased stability, and safety (Gilkey, 2019). The interactive risk associated with ATVs requires that riders exert more effort, stand frequently, and shift their weight to maintain control of the vehicle especially when turning, riding up, down, or across hills. The ATV is smaller, designed for one person, and inherently less stable because of its narrower wheelbase and higher center of gravity (Gilkey, 2019).

The MWCA is a unique agriculture organization with members that use ATVs and UTVs frequently, more so in the spring, summer, and fall. Spraying weeds using ATVs or UTVs in Montana and/or elsewhere consists of modifying the vehicle to hold fluid-filled tanks to carry herbicide. The operator rides along roadways and property lines spraying herbicides. The added tanks when filled with liquid raise the ATVs or UTVs center of gravity thus requiring more strength and body movement to control the vehicle. The higher stress and strain are concerning when a fatal outcome from a LOC and crash is 3.9 times higher on an ATV carrying a liquid load such as a herbicide tank (Shulruf & Balemi, 2010).

The relationship between the number of reported fatigue locations and the vehicle type or gender were evaluated using a Chi-square and GLM. The results of this evaluation resulted in p-values greater than 0.05, statistically insignificant. The relationship between the number of reported pain locations and the vehicle/gender using the same GLM resulted in a similar p-value > 0.05 . The low number of responses resulted in a poor goodness of fit in the model. Even though statistically, there were no significant relationships seen between fatigue or pain and vehicle operated or gender, there were higher frequencies of responses related to fatigue and pain in certain body locations (Figures 3 and 4). Figure 3 shows about half of the respondents indicated shoulders and lower back were the most common area of complaint for both ATV and UTV operation, this was consistent with prior investigation (Milosavljevic et al., 2010). These findings suggest that future research is warranted looking at how a tank-equipped vehicle affects the arm and back muscle activation. It is also noted from personal experience riding ATVs and spraying weeds, stress is greater on the upper extremity because one arm must hold the spray wand with one hand and driving with the opposite hand. The net effect is greater fatigue and pain from sustained static loading.

The age distribution was consistent with the group of MWCA personnel that were regional supervisors who completed the survey. There were very few young people, 4% < 24 years and only 3% that reported being older than 65 years that completed the survey. A study was completed in Australia that revealed that the number of fatal incidents on ATVs increases with age but decreases after age 65 (Fragar et al., 2007). This was also shown in the CPSC report where the age group 55+ had about double the off-highway fatalities in contrast to the 16-24 age group (2020). The LOC hazards of operating ATVs are strongly correlated with human behavior because of the interactive risk associated with vehicle control. Training on vehicle operation and risk control is offered by the ASI and Recreational Off-Highway Vehicle Association (ROHVA) and strongly suggested for those with careers requiring ATV and/or UTV use on the job (ASI, 2021; ROHVA, 2021; Shulruf & Balemi, 2010).

5. CONCLUSION

It appears that there is a relationship between ATV and/or UTV use and perceived stress and strain in the arms and lower back and other areas of the body. This pilot study focused on identifying regions of the body experiencing stress and strains. Multiple regions of the body were identified with differences between vehicle types. The results of this pilot study provide a basis for further research investigating, measuring, and evaluating the stresses in the arm, legs, and back when performing specific tasks such as spraying weeds. The trends in use of ATVs and UTVs in occupational settings will likely increase as more industries find applications for the units. The hope is further research may lead to a deeper understanding of human behavior and interactive risk so that prevention strategies can be developed and implemented driving down the numbers of LOC events and resulting injuries and fatalities.

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Behavioral Economics of Safety Culture Management in Companies

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KEYWORDS

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ABSTRACT

Most businesses are more concerned with making money and increasing profits than with ensuring the safety of their workers. Why do business leaders and employers refuse to invest in safety culture, as though they are unconcerned or unresponsive to risky work practices that result in disasters, incidents, family pain, and long-term consequences? They are probably unaware that the benefits of implementing safety in any company, large or small, far outweigh the financial benefits of not doing so.

1. INTRODUCTION

Profits should not be made at the expense of the health and safety of employees. Paul O'Neill saw that safety is an opportunity to boost profit and productivity while lowering medical and compensation costs and improving the bottom line (Berthold, 2016). Reduced lost employee hours, hospital costs, sick leave, pollution costs, property damages, and insurance premiums are all benefits of a safe work environment, all of which lead to higher productivity (Ekenedo, 2013).

Over the years, it has been debated whether willful violations of systems rules and procedures can be explained by system designers and managers failing to follow some behavioral economics propositions: firstly, unclear rules; secondly, delayed or ambiguous feedback; and thirdly, conflicts between high and low-level safety commitments (Battmann and Klumb, 1993).

Organizational safety culture management is heavily influenced by behavioral economics. The theoretical underpinning of safety culture is that it represents how people think and behave in connection to safety; it is a proactive method for enhancing occupational safety by focusing on the company's safety systems and its people's safe behaviors. The term "safety culture" has several definitions (Vu & De Cieri, 2014). Employee perceptions, attitudes toward organizational safety goals, everyday safe behavior, and the company's safety mechanisms to support safe behavior are all represented in the existing safety culture, according to the American Petroleum Institute (2015). (Cooper, 2018).

According to the Journal of Accounting and Economics, U.S. company executives, under market pressure to fulfill profitability expectations, may put workers' health and safety at risk in order to please investors (Smith, 2017). More than forty standards dealing with occupational safety and health have been adopted by the ILO, providing tools for governments, businesses, and workers to set procedures

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that ensure optimal workplace safety. However, the reality for millions of workers is quite different (ILO, 2021). Behavioral economics can help us discover solutions to regulate or ethically influence organizational biases and cognitive limitations, in order to help create company value (Deloitte, 2021). According to the ILO (2021b), health and safety management is an essential part of running a company to ensure that dangers and risks cannot harm employees.

This study examined the role of behavioral economics in safety management in order to create more lucrative judgments by analyzing potential concerns with at-risk behavior perception.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The economic benefits of health and safety management are enormous, with a return of 2.2 Euros for every Euro invested in OSH (Tanya, 2021). According to recent studies, it is behavioral economics 'money' that provides the solution, as well as actionable insights for employers and governments as they bargain between safety management and profits (Jaggi, 2021). Behavioral science insights can help firms better understand how they make financial decisions related to health, safety, and the environment (HSE). As a result, behavioral economics is critical to a company's long-term safety culture implementation (Dash, 2020).

Behavioral economics refers to the economic decision-making processes of individuals and institutions (Academy 4SC, 2021). Safety culture is about the values, beliefs, norms, practices, competencies and behaviors of an organization in relation to HSE. (Drummond and Pietikainen, 2021). International studies on the return on investment in prevention show that every unit invested in safety and health generates a potential benefit of more than two units of positive economic effects. The improvement of safety and health protection in the company does not necessarily mean an increase in expenditure (DGUV, 2021).

The Covid-19 situation underlines the importance of the balance between economy and health, taking into account the interactions between safety and microeconomics, in order to support this type of decision-making in the sense of a cost-benefit analysis and profitability analysis in safety culture management (Chao et al., 2021). The Covid-19 pandemic has shown how important occupational safety and health protection are for protecting the health of employees, for the smooth functioning of our societies, and for economic and social action. The European Commission renews its commitment to update health and safety at work by adopting the EU Strategic Framework for Health and Safety at Work 2021-2027; it set out the measures needed to improve the health and safety of workers over the next few years (European Commission, 2021).

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research has shown that the behavioral economics of safety culture management is a relevant, critical and important concern for companies. With that in mind, it was a good idea to examine various findings from field workers, especially during the Covid-19 pandemic when economic security issues were a real concern. Both primary data (interviews, discussions) and secondary data (incident and accident rates) were collected. Interviews based on open-ended questions and personal in-depth discussions with 309 HSE, medical, educational, management and psychiatric professionals were conducted over a time period of two months (from June to July 2021) using remote data collection techniques from various locations and organizations in India. The non-random convenience, as well as snowball sampling techniques, were used to collect the relevant data. The participants were selected from the researcher's contact list and invited via WhatsApp and email to take part in the online survey.

4. DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

A key element of this research was data collection, which was carried out by means of controlled interviews and questionnaire surveys. A total of 500 people participated in this study, 309 of whom completed a field-of-action survey with the researcher. These research participants had introduced a behavioral safety culture in their workplaces. The research participants involved CEOs, directors, managers, department heads and security professionals from public and private industrial sectors, including chemicals, construction, gas, energy and steel.

Roughly 84% of the study participants said that they did not support a zero-harm policy. Almost 90% of the study participants felt that the main reasons why Indian companies are unwilling to spend on safety are: ignorance, cost, wrong regulation, abuse of regulation, and the reluctance of workers. The study participants noted that behavior and safety are positively correlated, and that when doing root-cause analysis, the underlying cause of safety implementation is people's behavior. The study participants (about 78%) also noted that increased involvement in safety awareness reflects a good safety culture.

The greatest challenge in the implementation of the behavioral safety culture program is the involvement of all employees, including contract employees, which is only possible when the fear of making punctual corrections to endangered behavior at the workplace has been removed from the minds. In other words, the approval of every employee is paramount to a successful implementation. This can be demonstrated by department heads and other senior leadership teams through visible actions that strengthen safe behavior and reduce risk behavior (Cooper, 2020). Employees should be encouraged to report any risky behavior openly and without fear, using the 'no-fault, no mistake, no name's method with the main objective of correcting behavior on the ground in order to reduce the risk of accidents or incidents, as suggested by 86% of the study participants.

The principle of positive safety culture management ensures that companies generate sustainable profits. Eight-eight percent of the study participants believed that a strong safety culture ensured that everyone is empowered, responsible for safety, and pursues safety on a daily basis by making punctual corrections of unsafe behavior without fear, with the primary goal of Zero Harm for everyone. The study participants feel that when an employee is valued, heard and really cared for, his or her attitude towards the company becomes different in a positive way. This, consequently, forces management to create an environment in which employees feel comfortable when they encounter safety risks or risky behavior (Michie, 2020).

The study participants (89%) also noted that organizations that do implement a behavioral safety approach ensure that no one is being harmed. However, they noted that establishing a safety culture is not only associated with a change in behavior, but also with a change in the mindset. The economics of implementing a behavioral safety culture in companies was noted by 82% of the study participants who indicated that unsafe practice leads to disaster and that every disaster, like road accidents, railway accidents, fire accidents, etc., is beyond an economic evaluation;

Generally speaking, the study participants felt that Indian companies do not appear to be aware that spending on safety is an investment and not an expense!

5. CONCLUSIONS

During the past 15 months, the world has witnessed the direct and indirect effects of a pandemic that took the lives of millions of people around the world and left millions at risk with its devastating and

painful effects. Due to the lack of awareness among urban and suburban communities, the spread of the pandemic had been uncontrollable! This could have been avoided, or the extent of the harm reduced if people had behaved responsibly by following various Covid-19 appropriate behaviors to limit the deadly effects (Nature Human Behavior, 2020).

By all means, a strong safety culture begins with the visible commitment of management and highly committed and capable employees at all levels. This would lead to satisfied stakeholders through reduced costs, increased reliability, reduced maintenance and better product quality, as well as benefits through motivated employees and satisfied customers; this could have direct consequences on business sustainability and profitability.

Eighty-one percent of the study participants stated that the behavioral safety culture was an instrument with which risks from occupational health and safety, as well as process safety, can be successfully limited. This behavioral science approach is currently being used successfully in numerous companies around the world (Geller, 2001).

There is a need to expand the behavioral safety culture program to include employee families and other key stakeholders in society, especially children and adolescents. This could only be achieved through the intervention of educational institutions and public forums that raise awareness of a behavioral safety culture in order to make it a way of life! Occupational health and safety management (OSH) can and should be viewed in monetary terms as part of a business system (Eastern Kentucky University, 2021). Annual safety reviews are critical to continued development; these are often not actively addressed by managers. What is important is that changing the hierarchy of safety controls at the sites is very important; this is also not so strongly emphasized by HODs. Most importantly, every employee plays 5 minutes of safety time every day, which is set as the SOP, an important role in developing a good safety culture. Performance reviews must be used as part of the safety culture to maintain a safe work environment (Hestbak, 2019).

The development of an interdependent safety culture is on the agenda for future-oriented companies in order to ensure long-term sustainability. The best way to identify company culture is by how its employees behave outside of the workplace. A common vision of the people of a zero-harm future would be the foundation of a safety culture that is reflected in safety beliefs, values, attitudes and daily behavior. It is important to motivate and motivate employees to pursue the behaviors that contribute to a strong HSE culture (Scace, 2018).

6. SCOPE OF FUTURE RESEARCH

It is important to remember that poor occupational health and safety costs money. Good occupational safety is good for business (EU-OSHA, 2021). The industry longs for social well-being. Safety is the core value in the industries of developed nations. The benchmarking of the safety statistics of all industrial nations has changed dramatically. Environmental standards are also implemented as disciplinary benchmarks. Due to the spread of the Covid-19 pandemic, occupational safety standards have been drastically improved. But, safety goes far beyond that! It still starves for benchmarking excellence. The number one cause of any injury caused by an incident is behavior. This also has a cascading effect on environmental health (Chao et al., 2021). Understanding changes in working conditions and deciding on company practices for safety, health and wellbeing would be critical (Glorian et al., 2021). Anticipate, prepare and invest now in resilient occupational safety and health systems (ILO, 2021a). Understanding the biggest risks in the workplace is the first step to better protecting employees and the bottom line (Liberty Mutual Insurance, 2021).

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